

Table 2. Scoring systems for drought resistance at reproductive phase, 12–15 days after start of stress.

Decimal score	Heading ^a	Panicle exertion	Panicle size	Spikelet fertility (%)	Grain filling	Leaf rolling
1	No delay	Full	Normal	91–100	Mostly well-filled	Slight folding
3	Delayed by less than 1 wk	Full	Normal	76–90	Mostly well-filled	Half-rolling
5	Delayed by more than 1 wk	Partial ^b	Slightly reduced	51–75	Mostly half-filled	Full to tight
7	Delayed by more than 2 wks	Half-exserted	Reduced by half	11–50	Half-filled to empty	Tight
9	No heading until soil moisture is replenished	Half-exserted	Reduced by half	0–10	Mostly empty	Tight

^aLate varieties usually recover and produce grains when the rains set in before the end of the test. Reproductive scores are usually less reliable for the late-maturing varieties when rainfall is frequent before the dry season ends. ^bExcept for inherent agronomic traits.

Table 3. Scoring system for recovery (scores taken 1 or 2 days after rewatering).

Decimal scale	Description
1	90% of plants produce new leaves and tillers 1-2 days after watering (or a rain)
3	75% of plants produce new leaves and tillers 1-2 days after watering
5	75-90% of plants produce new leaves and tillers 3-4 days after watering
7	50-75% of plants produce new leaves and tillers 4-5 days after watering
9	Fewer than 50% of plants produce new leaves or tillers 1 week after watering

tems that provide separate criteria for different variety groups, for responses at the vegetative and reproductive stages, and for recovery after rain (Tables 1, 2, 3). Our system should supplement the brief scales given in the 1980 Standard Evaluation System for Rice. ■

Pest management and control DISEASES

Studies on *Claviceps oryzae sativae*, the incitant of false smut of rice

R. A. Singh, presently senior postdoctoral fellow, Plant Pathology Department, International Rice Research Institute; and R. K. Verma, Plant Pathology Department, G. B. Pant University of Agriculture and Technology, Pantnagar 263145, India

Nutritional studies of the fungus *Claviceps oryzae sativae* showed that growth was maximum on yeast peptone potato dextrose agar, followed by that on oatmeal yeast extract, rice yeast dextrose, yeast extract, rice polish, Richard's, Lilly and Barnett's, Raulin's, Coon's, Leonian, Brown's and Czapek's agar. Seven carbon sources were tested. Growth was maximum on maltose followed by mannitol, galactose, starch, sucrose, lactose, and sorbose, and control. Among the nitrogen sources evaluated, asparagine supported maximum growth of the fungus followed by ammonium oxalate, ammonium chlo-

ride, potassium nitrate, peptone, control, sodium nitrate, and tris (hydroxymethyl) methylamine.

Eight isolates of the fungus collected from different parts of India were grouped into four strains on the basis of morphological and cultural characters. A cytological study of the germinating conidium indicated that mitotic division and germ tube formation occur simultaneously. Subsequent nuclear divisions occur quickly to meet the requirement of secondary conidia produced at the rate of 1 nucleus/conidium.

Survival studies of conidia, pseudosclerotia, and true sclerotia showed that the first two propagules do not survive for long either at room temperature or in the field and probably do not serve as the source of primary inoculum in northern India. However, true sclerotia survived sufficiently long at room temperature and in the field and probably act as the primary inoculum source.

Fungicidal evaluation in vitro showed

that Du-Ter, TCMTB, Brestanol, Aureofungin, and Difolatan were effective against the pathogen. Alkaloids were detected in both pseudosclerotia and true sclerotia, which gave positive test for a carbohydrate, glycolipid and for an unsaturated compound, but they differed on the basis of the presence or absence of aldehyde or ketones, or both. ■

Mechanical separation of paddy seeds as applied to plant pathology

K. M. Rajan, Rice Research Station (RRS), Moncompu, Kerala, India 688503

Two major plant pathological constraints in rice production in the Kuttanad tract of Kerala, India, are sheath blight *Corticium sasakii* and sheath rot *Acrocyndrium oryzae*. Sheath rot is relatively new and is difficult to control through chemical means because it is seedborne.

Seed treatment with fungicides

generally does not kill fungi present inside glumes. Although treating seeds with hot water is effective against internal pathogens, the process is precise and difficult for farmers to adopt.

Infected seeds weigh less than healthy and fully filled grains; so mechanical separation based on specific gravity would help differentiate healthy and diseased seeds.

In a field experiment during the punja season (Oct-Jan) at the Moncompu RRS, seeds of Bharathy (highly susceptible to sheath rot) were treated with different concentrations of common salt. Seeds that sank to the bottom in each solution were washed in three changes of clean water and broadcast.

Both sheath blight and sheath rot were reduced as salt concentration increased (see table). In general, sheath blight incidence was low but sheath rot disease was moderate up to 7.5% concentration of the salt solution. Reduction in sheath rot at a

Intensity of sheath blight and sheath rot diseases in seeds treated with different concentrations of salt solution. Kerala, India.

Concn (%) of salt solution	Sheath blight score ^a	Sheath rot score ^b
0.0 (untreated control)	1.8	3.6
2.5	1.5	3.6
5.0	0.6	3.1
1.5	0.4	3.1
10.0	0.2	2.6
12.5	0.1	1.4
15.0	0.3	0.9
17.5	0.2	0.3
20.0	0.2	0.1
C.D.	0.8	1.0

^a1976 Standard Evaluation System for Rice (SES) scale: 1 = lesions limited to lower 1/4 of leaf sheaths, 9 = lesions reaching top of tillers; severe infection on all leaves. ^b1976 SES scale: 1 = less than 1% [of tillers affected] (= to resistant check), 9 = 50-100% (= to susceptible check).

concentration of 15% was significant compared to that at lower concentrations.

Mechanical separation of seeds by the method used in this experiment is cheap and simple, and can easily be used by farmers. ■

Transmission of *Rhynchosporium oryzae* Hashioka and Yokogi by seed

S. Amu Singh and P. K. Sen Gupta. Plant Pathology Department, Bidhan Chandra Krishi Viswavidyalaya, Kalyani-741235, West Bengal, India

The transmission of *Rhynchosporium oryzae*, the pathogen for rice leaf scald, was investigated in three separate trials. In the first, the fungus was detected by the standard blotter method in seeds of Cheena I collected from a heavily infected farmer's field. The seeds were examined periodically for the presence of the fungus. In the second test, surface-sterilized seeds of Cheena I were rolled in actively sporulating culture of the fungus and were sown in sterilized potted field soils. In another test, seeds from severely infected plants of Cheena I and IET2914 were similarly sown in sterilized field soil. Observations on the appearance of the disease on the seedlings raised in the two tests were recorded until the plants reached maturity.

Isolation of *Rhynchosporium oryzae* from rice seeds of cultivar Cheena I. West Bengal, India.

Date of observation ^a	Seeds(%) giving the fungus	
	Unsterilized	Sterilized
1 Aug 1977	1.14	0
20 Aug	1.13	0
1 Sep	0.86	0
1 Oct	0.61	0
1 Nov	0.00	0
18 Nov	0.00	0

^aSeeds were collected on 26 July 1977.

With the blotter method, the leaf scald fungus could be detected from seed samples of cultivar Cheena I within the first 3 months of collection (see table). The percentage of fungal isolations gradually declined with time of storage. Low percentages of seeds (0.61-1.14%) yielded the fungus. Success in isolating the fungus from unsterilized seed samples and failure to do so from surface-sterilized seeds indicated that the pathogen was externally seedborne.

The plants raised from seeds artificially inoculated with the fungus and from seeds harvested from scald-infected, plants of both Cheena I and IET2914 remained disease free until maturity.

Although a low percentage of rice seeds may have borne the leaf scald fungus *R. oryzae*, the exact role of this seedborne infection in causing the disease could not be established. ■

Studies on sheath rot of rice

R. A. Singh, presently senior postdoctoral fellow, Plant Pathology Department, International Rice Research Institute; and C. A. Raju, Plant Pathology Department, G. B. Pant University of Agriculture and Technology, Pantnagar 263145, India

Sheath rot of rice caused by *Sarocladium oryzae* (Sawada) Gams and Hawkeworth has recently become serious in northern India.

A partially selective medium for the fungus has been developed by incorporating 100 ppm Dithane 2-78 and 750 ppm Dicrystin S in Kirchoffs medium. The infected leaf sheaths and grains from diseased panicles were stored at room temperature (8-40° C) and under field conditions to study the survival of the pathogen. The fungus was isolated periodically from diseased parts on Kirchoffs medium. The fungus survived as long as 4 months in seed and 7 months in leaf sheath kept at room conditions and as long as 10 months in leaf sheaths in the field.

The disease development and the meteorological factors for the corresponding period were compared for 3 consecutive seasons from 1976-78 kharif to determine the most favorable conditions. Disease development was maximum when the minimum temperature was 17-20° C and the minimum relative humidity, 40-50% at flowering. The maximum temperature, maximum relative humidity, rainfall, and sunshine could not be correlated with disease severity.

Of the inoculation methods tried, injection of the spore suspension and placement of the pathogen grown on pearl millet inside the boot leaf sheath 7-4 days before flowering gave maximum disease in the field.

Five varieties — Basmati 370, Chinsurah Boro II, Hom Thong, Sigadis,